

ASSESSMENT OF THE ACTIVITIES OF NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL SEED COUNCIL (NASC) ON ADOPTION OF IMPROVED RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.) SEEDS BY HOST COMMUNITIES

Abenga, J.K., Idu, E.E. and Fadiji T.O.

Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology, Faculty of Agriculture
University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

Correspondence author: janetabenga5050@gmail.com; 08035968364

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the activities of the National Agricultural Seed Council (NASC), Abuja on the adoption of improved rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) seed by Host Communities. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to purposively select 398 rice farmers in Kwali Area Council FCT, Abuja. The results were analysed by well-structured questionnaires, descriptive statistics, and Logit Regression. The socio-economic characteristics of the rice farmers were analyzed and their involvement and benefits from NASC activities were equally examined. 95.7% of the farmers were aware of the council's activities. 94.5% of the farmers participated in the activities while 95% of these participated in the farmers' field day, 88.9% participated in training activities, 86.7% participated in green field day, 51.5% participated in seed fair and 39.7% participated in road walk activities. 88.9% of the farmers participated in training sessions, 97.4% adopted the use of improved seeds provided by NASC while 19.3% of farmers experienced a "fair" increase in production and 2.3% had a "great" improvement in their rice farming activities. 2.3% did not experience any increase in production following the adoption of the new technologies. 96% experienced improved awareness of enhanced farming practices while 95.7% of the farmers benefited from access to improved rice seeds. 85.9% of farmers experienced significant improvement in manpower development while about 70.4% benefited from access to farming machinery. The value of the Nagelkerke R squared is 0.243 and 75.7% is due to error or variables not captured in the model. This implied that years of farming experience and farm size were significant at 10% level of probability. The host communities are not only aware but have benefitted immensely from the various activities of NASC on improved rice seeds.

Keywords: Adoption, Community, National Agricultural Seed Council, Seeds, Improved rice seeds

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is blessed with suitable ecologies that enable her to grow different varieties of rice which if properly cultivated can boost rice production to meet the domestic food demands. About 4.9 million hectares of Nigerian land area is suitable for rice production but only 3 million hectares are being cultivated. Kebbi State of Nigeria is the highest producer of rice at about 2.05 million metric tonnes in the wet season and 1.051 million in the dry season. WATCO Rice Limited operates a state-of-the-art rice mill in Kebbi State which is the largest rice mill in West Africa (Accret User, 2022).

A lot of studies on rice production have been done earlier and many theories have been propounded to help solve the problem of increasing demand for rice consumption but none has categorically emphasized the place of certified and improved rice seed with NASC as a case study. This research work is thus aimed at looking at what NASC can contribute in terms of increasing rice production through improved technology.

In every agricultural practice, the importance of viable seeds cannot be over-emphasized. The small-holding rice farmer has several limitations in terms of using the appropriate seed in his rice farming because of poverty, ignorance and accessibility to the right seeds. This hampers the bumper harvest that would have been attained hence the production of enough rice yield to meet the demand of the teaming population remains unattainable. The issue of improved and reliable certified rice seeds as well as high-quality foundation rice seeds being made available to the smallholding rice farmer in the study area will go a long way to improve their production since good viable seed alone can improve the farmer's yield with up to 40%.

Certified and improved rice seed will do even much more than this and in addition to other farm inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides and other good agricultural practices.

Any variety that has been bred using formal plant breeding methods is called an improved variety. Bred cultivars that have been recycled but still maintain their characteristic attributes are also referred to as improved varieties. Improved high-quality seed or planting material results from conscious varietal improvement which generates good genetic material that can be massively propagated by the rice farmers. For example, the adoption of some of these improved varieties can increase production by over 200kg/ha or even 400kg/ha. (Osho-Lajungu, 2023)

In Nigeria, the mandate to improve rice production and development of new varieties is given to the National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Badeggi in Niger State because of the high consumption rate of the commodity in the country. Research on rice in Nigeria is mainly carried out by the government or a few private and non-governmental agencies as well as some research organizations. The main institutions involved are the National Research Cereals Centre (NCRI), the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) and the National Agricultural Seed Council (NASC). Our field of study in this work is the NASC. Therefore, this study is aimed at investigating how NASC has helped the rice farmers in the host communities to adopt improved rice seed variety in Kwali Area Council, Abuja.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research methodology will involve a mix of relevant quantitative and qualitative techniques. The research will be designed with conceptual framework and empirical study to answer the questions raised therein. This section will discuss and provide details of the research design and methodologies employed in the study.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Classification of the population is the first step in the sampling procedure, namely; the sector or element under investigation, the sampling unit, area or extent of investigation and the duration of investigation (Brodrick, 2014). Under this investigation are farmers in the host communities specifically processing (value adds) and trading of rice. The sampling units cover households involved in crop production and those involved in agricultural seeds value chain such as production, processing and marketing of agricultural seeds in the host communities (Morse, 2019).

Multi-stage and proportional sampling procedures were used for the study. In the first stage, 4 wards in Kwali Area Council were purposively selected for the study. In the second stage, one community was purposively selected from each of the selected ward. In the third stage, each of the selected

community were divided into two each making a total of four wards, four communities and eight units were used in the study. The sample size for the study was 398 rice farmers as respondents for the study.

The concept of participatory rural appraisal, focus group discussion and Pear man ranking were employed here using questionnaires and interview schedules among the Three hundred and ninety- eight (398) rural rice farmers from Kwali Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory. Questionnaires were used in collecting data from the respondents who were the source of primary data.

Data Analysis

Appropriate models were developed to analyze the specific objectives. The various models so specified were highlighted under separate headings in line with the objectives of the study.

Socio-economic characteristics (age, education, land ownership, etc. frequency and simple percentage technique was adopted to measure this variable) Access to improved rice seeds (binary: Yes/No was employed to measure this variable).

Logit Model Analysis

Following Ahmed *et al.* (2015), was used to analyze the influence of the socio-economic characteristics of the rice producers on the adoption of improved rice seeds in the study area. Logit model is stated explicitly as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \mu_i$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents presented in Table 1 reveals that most of the farmers were male (88%) which aligns with the findings of Idu *et al.* (2020) where they found that most of the respondents in their study were male.

About 92% of the farmers surveyed are

married, making marriage the predominant marital status. This suggests that most of the farmers are likely to be in stable family units thus having various implications for agricultural activities (Apta *et al.*, 2018).

The household distribution of the farmers revealed that majority of them had large households. About 60% of the respondents had at least 7 persons in their household,

while 21.4% of farmers have a household size of at most 3 persons. The average household size of the respondents was 7. A larger household size could impact several factors, such as the availability of labour for farming activities, household food consumption, and economic needs. Larger households might rely more on farming for sustenance and income, which could influence their agricultural practices and productivity (Kassie *et al.*, 2013).

The age distribution showed that most (39.9%) of the rice farmers were between 41 and 50 years, while about 3.3% of them were 61 years and above. The average age of 48 suggests that most farmers are in their late 40s, confirming that the dominant age group is middle-aged (41-50 years) and that the overall population of rice farmers skews toward an older demographic. The result further revealed that 67.1% of the farmers had been producing rice for at least 21 years, while those who had been cultivating rice for 10 years or less accounted for 4.1% of the respondents. The mean (average) years of farming experience among these farmers is 26 years. This suggests that the majority of farmers in this group have a long history of rice cultivation, contributing to a high average number of years of experience. The results show that the majority of the farmers in the study have completed secondary school education (31.1%), which indicates that a significant proportion of the farmers have a basic level of formal education while (27.3%) have no formal education at all which may have implications on their ability to adopt new farming technologies or practices that require specialized knowledge. Nwokoye *et al.* (2019). This further agrees with the assertions of Oduro- Ofori that education level is a great factor in the farmer's ability to adopt new innovations or

reject them. Ninety –six point three percent (96.3%) of

the farmers had farm size ranging from 1 to 3 hectares while only 1.3% possessed farmlands of more than 3 hectares revealing that the farmers had an average of 1.6 hectares of farmland. About 66% of the farmers produced between 1,000 to 5,000kg while 30.5% of them produced between 5,001 and 10,000 kg while 2.8% of the farmers produced at least 10,000kg, 2.6% of them produced less than 1,000 kg of rice.

The average output of all farmers was 12,397.08 kg, which is relatively high compared to the individual production groups which suggests that a few farmers with very high production levels may be significantly increasing the overall average. Gailhard, I. U., and Bojnec (2015)

The result of the annual income distribution of the rice farmers is also presented in Table 4.1 showing that 72.1% had annual income of 100,001 to 500,000 naira, 14.1% made at most 100,000 while the remaining 13.9% made more than 500,000 annually. The average annual income of the rice farmers is 429108.58. Overall, the distribution shows a concentration of rice farmers earning between 100,001 to 500,000 naira annually, with fewer farmers at the extremes of the income range. The average income reflects that the majority are closer to the middle or higher end of this range. This agrees with the findings of Rokundo, Emmanuel, Ojong, Paul Jnr, Haile, Padjja and Dhebbi(2023) where it was reported that all identified characteristics have a directional relationship with adoption and improved seeds and technology have positive effects on household income where it is adopted.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Rice Farmers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Gender			
Male	344	88.0	
Female	54	12.0	
Marital Status			
Single	9	2.2	
Married	366	92.0	
Divorced	4	1.0	
Widowed	19	4.8	
Household Size			
1-3	85	21.4	
4-6	75	18.6	
7-9	11	30	7
>9	9	30	
Age			
<30	11	4	
31-40	69	17.5	
41-50	159	39.9	48
51-60	140	35.2	
>60	14	3.4	
Farming Experience (Years)			
<5	5	1.3	
6-10	11	2.8	
11-20	104	26.3	
21-30	153	38.5	26
>30	113	28.6	
Educational Level			
No formal education	107	27.3	
Primary	117	29.8	
Secondary	122	31.1	
Tertiary	58	11.8	
Farm Size (kg)			
< 1	7	1.8	
1 - 3	383	96.3	1.6
4 - 6	8	1.9	
Output			
=1,000	10	1.75	
1,001-5,000	260	66.0	12397.08
5,001-10,000	118	30.5	
>10,000	10	1.75	
Annual Income			
=100,000	58	14	
100,001-500,000	284	72.1	429108.58
500,001-1,000,000	30	7.6	
>1,000,000	26	6.3	
Membership of Cooperatives			
Yes	387	97.2	
No	11	2.8	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Awareness of NASC Activities among Farmers

From Table 2, 95.7% of the farmers reported being aware of the council's activities which indicates that the council has effectively reached and informed most of the rice farmers in the area about its operations and initiatives. Thijssen and Agbara (2023), published a report on the collaborative seeds programme between Nigeria and Netherlands, they indicated that the programme has made significant progress in reaching farmers while 4.3% of the farmers reported that they were not aware of any activities conducted by the NASC.

Table 2: Awareness of NASC Activities on Improved Rice Varieties by the respondents

Awareness of NASC Activities on Improved Rice Varieties	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	381	95.7
No	17	4.3
Total	398	100

Source: Computed from field data, 2024.

Figure 1: Awareness of NASC Activities on Improved Rice Varieties

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

NASC Activities Participated in By Rice Farmers Table 3 indicates a high level of engagement among the rice farmers with the outreach activities of the National Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC). 94.5% of the farmers reported participating in these activities suggesting that the NASC's outreach programs are highly effective in encouraging farmer participation. This aligns with the assertions of Okikioluwa and Shin (2024) in their study on factors influencing the use of improved maize seeds in seeds demonstration programmes. The substantial involvement of farmers likely reflects the relevance and appeal of the council's activities to their needs and interests.

Figure 2 shows the activity with the highest participation by the farmers as farmers' field day 95%, about 88.9% participated in training activities, 86.7% of them participated in green day field while 51.5% of them participated in seed fair. Only 39.7% participated in road walk activities.

Farmers' field day saw the highest level of participation, with 95% of the farmers taking part. This indicates that farmers' field day is the most popular or widely attended activity among the farmers, suggesting it is highly valued or effectively organized. Approximately 88.9% of the farmers participated in training sessions. This high level of involvement shows that the training activities are also well-received and significant to the farmers, likely providing them with valuable skills or knowledge. About 86.7% of the farmers took part in green day field. Suggesting that it is another important activity for farmers, though slightly less popular than the Farmers Field Day and training sessions. 51.5% of the farmers participated in the seed fair suggesting that while the seed fair is a notable activity, it has lower participation compared to the other events which could be due to various factors such as timing, relevance, or logistics. The lowest participation rate was for road walk activities, with only 39.7% of the farmers involved.

Figure 2: NASC Activities Participated in by the Rice Farmers

Adoption of Improved Seed by Farmers technologies they adopted. The majority of Table 3 reveals that a significant majority of farmers reported a "very much" increase in farmers 97.4% have adopted the use of production after adopting the new improved seeds provided by the National technologies. This suggests that the Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC). This majority of the farmers have experienced high adoption rate indicates that the vast substantial benefits from the technologies, majority of farmers have switched from indicating a strong positive impact on their their previous seeds to the improved agricultural output. 19.3% of farmers experienced a "fair" increase in production. varieties offered by the council. The overwhelming adoption rate implies that 2.3% of the farmers reported a "great" farmers generally view the improved seeds improvement in their rice farming activities. as beneficial. They likely perceive these This small percentage could suggest that seeds as offering advantages over their while some farmers saw a significant boost previous seed varieties, such as better in their overall farming activities, this was yields, enhanced disease resistance, or other less common compared to the broader desirable traits. The high adoption rate also positive impacts reported. suggests that the NASC's efforts to promote Another 12.3% of farmers stated that they improved seeds have been successful did not experience any increase in (Thijssen and Agbara, 2023). Overall, the production following the adoption of the data reflects a strong positive response from new technologies which indicates that a the farming community toward the small fraction of the farmers did not benefit from the technologies as expected possibly. The farmers were asked to indicate if they due to factors such as inadequate experienced any improvement in their rice implementation, external conditions, or farming activities as a result of the other variables.

Table 3: Adoption of Improved Seed by Farmers

No increase	49	12.3
Fairly increased	77	19.3
Very increased	263	66.1
Greatly increased	9	2.3
Total	398	100

Benefits from NASC by Rice Farmers gained a better understanding of Farmersmodern agricultural techniques and best The results presented in Table 4 provide an practices, 95.7% of farmers benefited from overview of National Agricultural Seeds access to improved rice seeds. This high Council (NASC) and its initiatives. 96% of adoption rate suggests that the availability farmers reported experiencing improved of better seed varieties was a significant awareness of enhanced farming practices. advantage for most farmers, contributing to This high percentage indicates that the better crop performance and potentially educational and informational aspects of higher yields. The result also revealed that NASC's outreach were very effective. 85.9% of farmers experienced significant

improvement in manpower development. Suggesting that the NASC’s activities included training programs or support that helped enhance the skills and capabilities of the labor. 70.4% of farmers benefited from access to farming machinery

These results suggest that the NASC’s initiatives have provided a wide range of

benefits to farmers, such as educational improvements, access to better resources, skills development, technological advancements, increased farm size and increased output and income while the major constraints to rice production were inadequate finance and credit facilities and poor soil fertility. Rashid, Abdulhamid, Enechi and Oyibo (2019)

Table 4: Benefits from NASC by Rice Farmers

Benefits	Frequency	Percentage
Improved machineries	280 381	70.4
Improved rice seeds	382 342	95.7
Improved awareness		96.0
Improvedmanpower development		85.9

Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Farmers on their Participation in NASC Activities

Objective 4, where a study of the effects of the socio-economic characteristics of the rice farmer in the study area was analyzed with particular emphasis on its influence on the adoption of improved rice seeds and improved technology as well as their

participation in NASC activities.

The effect of socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers on their participation in NASC activities was analyzed using logistic regression analysis, which is presented in Table 5. From the result, the value of the Nagelkerke R squared is 0.243, which implies that 24.3% of the variations in the dependent variable

can be explained by the independent variables. The remaining 75.7% is due to errors or variables not captured in the model. The result revealed that years of farming experience and farm size were significant at 10% level of probability.

Farm Size

The result indicates that farm size (0.059) has a positive and statistically significant effect on farmers’ participation in National Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC) activities, with significance at the 10% probability level. The term "positive

Farming Experience

The result from Table 5 indicates that years relationship" means that as the size of a of farming experience (0.073) have a farmer's farm increases, their level of positive and statistically significant effect participation in NASC activities also tends on farmers’ participation in National to increase. Essentially, larger farm sizes are Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC) associated with higher engagement in the activities, with the significance level set at council's activities. The result implies that 10%. The result implies that as farmers gain farmers with larger farm sizes are more more experience over time, they are more likely to participate in NASC activities.

This could be because experienced farmers resources availability, and economic might have a better understanding of the motivation. The relationship is statistically value of these activities, or they may have significant but at a less stringent level of more resources and time to engage. For confidence, suggesting a noteworthy but not NASC or similar organizations, this finding overwhelmingly robust correlation. This suggests that targeting more experienced study agrees with Gailhard, I. U., and farmers for engagement and outreach could Bojnec (2015) who found that farm size be beneficial. As stated by Blackstock *et al.* influences farmer’s decision to participate (2010), understanding the needs and in agri-environment measures. interests of these experienced farmers could help tailor programs to further enhance their participation.

Table 5: Effect of Socio Economic Characteristics of the Farmers on their Participation in NASC Activities

Variable	B	SE	Wald	Sig.
Gender	-.019	1.869	.000	.992
Marital status	.659	.569	1.339	.247
Household size	.027	.168	.026	.871
Age	-.045	.111	.168	.682
Year of farming experience	.032	.095	.112*	.073*
Educational level	-.457	.589	.603	.438
Farm size	1.791	.949	3.564*	.059*
Yield per annual	.000	.000	.016	.900
Income per annual	.000	.000	2.624	.105
Membership of cooperative	-18.653	11191.091	.000	.999
Constant	14.680	11191.093	.000	.999

Source: Field Survey, 2024 *Significant at 10%

Using logistic regression analysis, farming study, this research has contributed experience and farm size were significant significantly to the body of knowledge in at 10% level, which implied that years of identifying the impact of NASC on farming experience and farm size of improved rice seed as assessed by the rice farmers influence their participation in farmers in the host communities. From the NASC activities hence, the null hypothesis findings of this study, NASC and other was rejected. The value of the Nagelkerke agricultural policy makers can use larger R squared is 0.243, which implies that farm sizes and longer farming experience as 24.3% of the variations in the dependent a means to enhance the adoption of their variable can be explained by the improved rice seed varieties. Further studies independent variables. The remaining should be carried out on the impact of 75.7% is due to errors or variables not NASC on rice production in other parts of captured in the model.the federation to reduce hunger in the

country.

CONCLUSION

Drawing from the evidence presented in this

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